

Assessment of extraction techniques for total phenolics and flavonoids from *Annona muricata* seeds

S. Mahibalan^a, Ruben Sharma^a, Aditya Vyas^a, S. Ameer Basha^b and A. Sajeli Begum^{a*}

^aDepartment of Pharmacy, BITS-Pilani Hyderabad Campus, Jawahar Nagar, Shameerpet (M), Hyderabad-500 078, India

E-mail : sajeli1@rediffmail.com

^bRegional Agricultural Research Station, Acharya N. G. Ranga Agricultural University, Palem-509 215, Mahaboob Nagar District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract : The study describes the assessment of extraction techniques for total phenolics (TP) and flavonoids (TF) from the seeds of *Annona muricata*, which is commonly a neglected part of the fruit. Conventional extraction techniques like heat reflux, Soxhlet extraction, maceration with stirring and complementary extraction techniques like microwave assisted extraction (MAE) and ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE) were attempted. The TP and TF were determined spectrophotometrically using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and aluminium chloride, respectively. Among all extraction techniques, MAE accounted for higher extraction yield (16.2% w/w) followed by Soxhlet (9.68% w/w), maceration with stirring (8.12% w/w), heat reflux (6.76% w/w) and UAE (5.2% w/w). MAE method was optimised for various parameters like microwave power, irradiation time, solvent type, solvent concentration, preleaching time, solvent to material ratio and extraction cycle. Sonication time for UAE was also optimised. Higher TP content equivalent to gallic acid was obtained using heat reflux (0.147 ± 0.057 mg GAE/g) and Soxhlet methods (0.146 ± 0.012 mg GAE/g), followed by UAE, maceration with stirring and MAE techniques. TF content equivalent to quercetin was achieved higher (0.679 ± 0.288 mg QE/g) through MAE technique, which is almost double than the quantity obtained using UAE and maceration with stirring methods. The study clearly explicated the higher extraction yield and TF content but not TP, by MAE method compared to other techniques. Hence MAE under the optimised conditions is suitable for the targeted extraction of quercetin like flavonoids and conventional methods are appropriate for total phenolics extraction.

Keywords : *Annona muricata*, phenolics, flavonoids, microwave, ultrasound, conventional techniques.

Introduction

Extraction is the starting step in the qualitative and quantitative analysis of medicinal plant constituents. Preferably, an extraction technique should be rapid, simple, inexpensive, exhaustive with respect to the constituents to be analysed and with high degree of automation. An incomplete extraction process producing a poorly prepared extract may be therapeutically inactive and produce erroneous results. Generally traditional techniques like soxhlet, maceration, reflux and hydro distillation have been the first choice for extraction of phytochemicals. In recent times, modern techniques like microwave assisted extraction (MAE) and ultrasonic assisted extraction (UAE) have been proved to be promising extraction tools. However, the effectiveness and the efficient applicability of a

selected extraction technique depend on the selective bioactive principle of phytoextract.

Annona muricata L. (Annonaceae), a commercial fruit crop is commonly known as “guanabana” or “soursop” throughout the tropical regions of the world¹. The seeds of *A. muricata* are considered as rich source of acetogenins, isoquinoline alkaloids, leucoanthocyanins and triglycerides. *A. muricata* has a lengthy recorded indigenous use for treating liver problems, neuralgia, rheumatism and arthritis pain^{2,3}.

Phenolics and flavonoids are the important plant secondary metabolites proved as bioactive compounds. They are antioxidants capable of scavenging free superoxide radicals, anti-aging and reducing the risk of cancer. Most pharmaceuticals are based on plant component structures

like phenolics and flavonoids possessing varied biological activities⁴.

There are various sources for this group of compounds and *A. muricata* may become one among them. Search of literature disclosed that no comprehensive study has so far been carried out on the presence of phenolics and flavonoids in *A. muricata* seeds. Our preliminary phytochemical screening of *A. muricata* seed extract using ferric chloride reagent indicated the presence of phenolics and flavonoids.

Thus the study was extended to develop an effective method for extracting phenolics and flavonoids from the seeds of *A. muricata* without affecting its chemical nature. In general, total phenolics from medicinal herbs and dietary plants include phenolic acids, flavonoids, tannins, stilbenes, coumarins, quinines, lignans, etc. Traditionally, for the extraction of phenolics and flavonoids, heat reflux and Soxhlet extraction technique had been the first line of choice^{5,6}. The present study is focussed on comparing the percentage yield of total phenolics (TP) and flavonoids (TF) between conventional, ultrasound assisted and microwave assisted extraction technique for their large scale production. Further, the chemopreventive properties like antioxidant, anticarcinogenic, antimutagenic, antiinflammatory effects, etc. of phenolics and flavonoids⁴ necessitated the identification of a best source and extraction method.

Results and discussion

The selection of an extraction method would mainly depend on the advantages and disadvantages of the processes like extraction yield, complexity, production cost, environmental friendliness and safety. Keeping this in mind, the experimental results were analysed. The extraction of *A. muricata* seeds using different conventional and modern techniques like hot reflux, maceration with stirring, Soxhlet extraction, MAE and UAE was carried out. Methanol was used as a solvent, on safety grounds except MAE, where solvent optimisation is required. Among all extraction techniques, MAE accounted for higher extraction yield (16.2% w/w) followed by Soxhlet (9.68% w/w), maceration with stirring (8.12% w/w), heat reflux (6.76% w/w) and UAE (5.2% w/w). Many reports on the beneficial effects of MAE with respect to medicinal plants have been published, with significant improve-

ment over conventional extraction methods offering much lowered extraction time and enhanced efficiency⁷. The high extraction yield using MAE was achieved through optimisation of various parameters like microwave power, irradiation time, solvent type, solvent concentration, preleaching time, solvent into material ratio and extraction cycle.

The efficiency of extraction yield (% w/w) of *A. muricata* seed using different methods at optimised levels were compared and presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Effect of different techniques on extraction yield.

Optimization of MAE parameters :

The efficiency of MAE strongly relies on the selection of the operating conditions and the parameters affecting the extraction mechanisms and yield. The factors that may influence the performance of MAE are microwave power, irradiation time, type of solvent, composition of solvent, preleaching time, solvent to solid ratio and extraction cycle. In this study, these factors were investigated to obtain the maximum yield from *A. muricata* seeds.

Effect of microwave power :

Different microwave power was set at 140, 280, 420, 560 and 700 W to investigate the influence of microwave power at different irradiation time (2, 4 and 8 min) on the extraction yield of *A. muricata* seeds, when the other reaction conditions were set as follows : extraction solvent methanol, ratio of liquid to solid 25 ml/3 g and preleaching time 5 min. Fig. 2 shows that the % yield was greatly influenced by the microwave power. When microwave power was lower than 280 W, the % yield was increased with the increase of microwave power. When microwave power was higher than 280 W, the ex-

Fig. 2. Effect of microwave power on extraction yield.

traction efficiency decreased with the further increase of microwave power. This may be due to the increase in the temperature of the system. Increasing the temperature causes the solvent power to increase due to a drop in viscosity and surface tension⁸. High microwave power of MAE beyond the optimum operating power reduces extraction yield as thermo sensible compounds would risk thermal degradation. Hence, the highest extraction yield which was noticed at 280 W was considered optimum for maximum extraction.

Effect of irradiation time :

Duration of microwave irradiation of 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 min at the optimized microwave power (280 W) on the extraction yield of *A. muricata* was studied (Fig. 3), when the other reaction conditions were set as follows : extraction solvent ethanol, ratio of liquid to solid 25 ml/3g, preleaching time 5 min. MAE reached the highest

Fig. 3. Effect of irradiation time on extraction yield.

extraction yield of 7.98% (w/w) when irradiation time was 4 min. However, further increase in irradiation time resulted in decrease in the efficiency of extraction. This may be due to the longer extraction duration which cause over energy consumption or degradation of analytes in the seed. Hence, 4 min was selected for further experiments.

Effect of solvent type :

The selection of most suitable solvent in MAE extraction process for extracting the analytes of interest from the sample matrix is a fundamental step. It is important to note that the selection of a solvent for MAE cannot be deduced from the conventional extraction methods as solvents that work well in conventional techniques might not be a good solvent for MAE. Therefore, the MAE was performed at the optimized microwave power (280 W), irradiation time (4 min) and other parameters which are kept as constant as follows : ratio of liquid to solid 25 ml/3 g and preleaching time 5 min with five different polarity solvents. The results in Fig. 4 explicate that *n*-butanol gave highest extraction efficiency (10.46% w/w) for MAE, followed by chloroform (10.40% w/w), ethyl

Fig. 4. Effect of solvent type on extraction yield.

acetate (9.0% w/w), methanol (7.98% w/w) and acetone (7.8% w/w). Though the *n*-butanol gave higher extraction yield, due to its toxic effects with a high boiling point⁹ it was not taken into the consideration. Hence the next highest yield producing solvent i.e. chloroform was selected for further experiments.

Effect of aqueous chloroform concentration :

The influence of aqueous chloroform concentration in the efficiency of extraction is shown in Fig. 4. The experiments were carried out with the optimized parameters viz. microwave power 240 W, irradiation time 4 min, extraction solvent chloroform and other reaction conditions were set as follows : ratio of liquid to solid 25 ml/3 g, preleaching time 5 min. Fig. 5 demonstrates that the highest extraction yield was obtained when chloroform concentration was 100% (10.32% w/w). Addition of water resulted in significant fall in extraction yield. Hence, chloroform alone stands as a good solvent for extraction of *A. muricata* seeds.

Fig. 5. Effect of aqueous chloroform concentration on extraction yield.

Effect of preleaching time :

Preleaching time can be defined as the contact time between sample matrix and extracting solvent before microwave irradiation. Fig. 6 explains that higher extraction yield (14.88% w/w) could be achieved at 10 min preleaching time when the parameters were kept as follows : microwave power 240 W, irradiation time 4 min, extraction solvent chloroform along with constant ratio of liquid to solid : 25 ml/3 g. Preleaching time of 10 min is favourable for enhancing the extraction yield which allows swelling of the plant matrix.

Fig. 6. Effect of preleaching time on extraction yield.

However, further increase in preleaching time did not show any promising effect on the extraction performance.

Effect of solvent to material ratio :

Once a suitable solvent has been decided upon, its quantity to material ratio has to be determined as it affects the extraction yield in most cases^{10,11}. To investigate the influence of solvent to material ratio on the extraction yield, several loading ratio (25 : 3, 30 : 3, 35 : 3, 40 : 3, 45 : 3, 50 : 3 and 55 : 3 ml/g) were examined. The results illustrated in Fig. 7 suggest that the extraction yield increases as the amount of solvent increase till the

Fig. 7. Effect of solvent to material ratio on extraction yield.

ratio of solvent to material reach 45 : 3, at which the yield reached its highest value (15.40% w/w) and then it decreases slightly. This was probably due to the larger volume of solvent which cause more absorption of microwave energy and thus sufficient microwave energy may not be available for facilitating cell breakage for effective leaching out of the target analytes¹².

Effect of extraction cycle :

The effect of repeated and successive extractions of the residue was investigated in this experiment. The extraction conditions were set at the optimum parameters obtained so far in the study. A second and third successive extraction of the residue yielded 5.36 and 3.08% w/w respectively. A successive fourth extraction did not show any significant yield. Henceforth, it was discovered that three extraction cycles would be the best to produce higher extraction yield.

Hence the final optimum extraction conditions as obtained from the present study are as follows : 280 W microwave power, 4 min irradiation time, chloroform as the extraction solvent, 10 min preleaching time, 45 : 3 (ml/3 g) as the solvent to material ratio and 3 extraction cycles.

Optimization of sonication time in UAE :

The effect of ultrasound on the extraction yield of *A. muricata* seed was investigated at 60 °C and the results were presented in Fig. 8. The highest yield (5.2% w/w) was obtained at 60 min. The further increase in the extraction time did not produce significant increment in the extraction yield. Hence the present investigation verified that 60 min would be the optimum sonication time to obtain the best yield. Based on the present data one can say that ultrasound may assist with extraction process

Fig. 8. Effect of sonication time in UAE.

both through cell disruption and by enhancing mass transfer in the boundary layer surrounding the solid matrix¹³. The energy generated from collapsing cavitation bubbles causes the disruption of cell walls and release of cellular materials, so the yield can be improved by the use of ultrasound¹⁴.

Estimation of TP and TF :

Quantification of TP and TF in each extract obtained from the optimized methods of MAE, UAE and other conventional techniques was done by UV spectrophotometry and the results are presented in Table 1. The TP analysis was based on the reduction of phosphotungstate-phosphomolybdenum complex (Folin-Ciocalteu reagent) by phenolate ion. The reduction of the complex, reflected by colour change (blue) will increase when the extract contain more phenolic compounds.

Table 1. Total phenolic and flavonoid content in *A. muricata* seeds following various extraction techniques

Extraction methods	Total phenolics (mg GAE/g)	Total flavonoid (mg QE/g)
Microwave	0.099 ± 0.039	0.679 ± 0.288
Heat reflux	0.147 ± 0.057	0.590 ± 0.378
Soxhlet	0.146 ± 0.012	0.525 ± 0.229
Ultra sonication	0.134 ± 0.103	0.323 ± 0.150
Maceration with stirring	0.134 ± 0.041	0.329 ± 0.306

Values are mean ± SD.

The results disclosed the extraction of higher TP under heat reflux (0.147 ± 0.057 mg GAE/g) and Soxhlet extraction method (0.146 ± 0.012 mg GAE/g) followed by UAE (0.134 ± 0.103 mg GAE/g) and maceration with stirring (0.134 ± 0.041 mg GAE/g) methods. MAE method yielded only 0.099 ± 0.039 mg GAE/g of TP.

These findings suggested that conventional techniques like heat reflux and Soxhlet method would be suitable for the better extraction of TP compounds when methanol was used as a solvent.

TF content was obtained more (0.679 ± 0.288 mg QE/g) using MAE technique which is nearly twice the quantity obtained through UAE and maceration with stirring methods. Hence the present study suggested MAE as the most appropriate method for the extraction of flavonoids and the process can be completed within 4 min which saves lot of time. Besides, the electrical energy and quantity of solvent consumed in MAE was the least which is an environment-friendly and eco-friendly feature.

In contrary to the poor yield of TP, a good yield of TF was obtained via MAE, which were calculated equivalent to gallic acid and quercetin content. The MAE proved to be efficient for TF was not effective in terms of TP. The study corroborated that the optimised conditions for MAE were suitable for preparing extracts enriched with flavonoids. The higher extractive yield and low level of TP obtained by MAE compared to conventional techniques may be due to the excess of heat produced during the extraction process causing leaking of impurities from the matrix and decomposition of phenolic compounds other than flavonoids.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Plant material and chemicals :

Dried seeds of *A. muricata* were collected from Trivandrum District, Kerala, India during the month of September 2011. The seeds were powdered and passed through the sieve # 60 to obtain a homogenous powder. Organic solvents were purchased from S.D. Fine Chemicals (Mumbai, India).

Apparatus and conditions :

The MAE was performed in a system comprised of a microwave extractor (CATA R) manufactured by Catalyst System (Pune, India) equipped with a magnetron of 2450 MHz with a nominal maximum power of 700 W, a reflux unit, 10 power levels, time controller, temperature sensor, exhaust system, beam reflector and a stirring device. The UAE extraction has been done using sonication

water bath (Fast Clean, Ultrasonic cleaner, model : N-50-vs, capacity 5 L, Life Care Equipments Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India)

Conventional extraction techniques :

Heat reflux extraction :

Accurately weighed 5 g of the powdered seed material was extracted with 100 ml methanol in round bottom flask by heat reflux extraction. The extraction was performed for 24 h at 60 °C. The extract was filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure to determine TP and TF. All the measurements were carried out in triplicate, and the data reported were mean \pm S.D.

Soxhlet extraction :

Exhaustive Soxhlet extraction was performed using a classical Soxhlet apparatus with accurately weighed 5 g of the powdered seed for 24 h at 60 °C. Extraction was performed with methanol as the extracting solvent. After extraction, the content was filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure to determine TP and TF. All the measurements were carried out in triplicate, and the data reported were mean \pm S.D.

Maceration with stirring extraction :

Accurately weighed 5 g of the powdered seed material was placed in a closed conical flask and the extraction was carried out with 100 ml methanol and continuous stirring was done with the help of magnetic stirrer. After 24 h of extraction at normal room temperature, the content was filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure to determine TP and TF. All the measurements were carried out in triplicate and the data reported were mean \pm S.D.

Ultrasonic assisted extraction (UAE) :

A sample of 5 g of powdered seed was kept in a glass flask containing 100 ml methanol. Ultrasound assisted extraction was performed in a sonication water bath at 60 °C for 5, 10, 20, 40 and 60 min of extraction time. The working frequency and the power were fixed at 33 ± 2 kHz and 120 W respectively. Quantification to determine TP and TF was carried out. All the measurements were carried out in triplicate, and the data reported were mean \pm S.D.

Microwave assisted extraction (MAE) :

Microwave assisted extraction was performed with 3 g of the homogenous powder mixed with 25 ml methanol.

After allowing a preleaching time of 5 min the suspension was irradiated with microwave at different experimental conditions for the optimization of the extraction parameters. The sample was treated under microwave irradiation in an intermittent way, i.e. irradiation : cooling : irradiation. The microwave irradiation time was 1 min and cooling time of 1 min was used to cool the sample solution between two irradiations. The total mass obtained from the optimized MAE was taken for the determination of TP and TF. All the measurements were carried out in triplicate, and the data reported were mean \pm S.D.

Determination of total phenolic (TP) content :

The TP of each extract was determined in triplicate using Folin-Ciocalteu procedures according to Xiaonan Lu *et al.*¹⁵ and Margaret Slavin *et al.*¹⁶. In short, 100 μ L of each extract, 500 μ L of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1 : 10) was mixed and incubated for 10 min at room temperature (25 °C). Then 1.5 ml of 7.5% (w/v) sodium carbonate was added. The mixture was allowed to stand in the dark for 2 h before measuring the absorbance at 765 nm using Jasco V-650 UV-Visible spectrophotometer against blank containing deionised water instead of sample extract. Results were reported as gallic acid equivalence (mg GAE) per gram of seed material.

Determination of total flavonoid (TF) content :

The TF of various extracts of *A. muricata* was determined in triplicate by a reported method^{17,18}. The reaction mixture containing 1 ml plant extract, 0.6 mL sodium nitrite (5% w/v), 0.5 mL aluminium chloride (10%, w/v), 3 mL sodium hydroxide (4.3%, w/v) was made up to 10 mL with water. In each step, 6 min time period was given for shaking to complete reaction at room temperature (25 °C). The solution was allowed to stand for 15 min and absorbance was measured at 500 nm on a Jasco V-650 UV-Visible spectrophotometer against blank containing deionised water instead of sample extract. Results were reported as quercetin equivalence (mg QE) per gram of seed material.

Conclusion

Extraction techniques have been assessed for the maximum yield and maximum content of phenolics and flavonoids from seeds of *A. muricata*. The data obtained

from the present study described that MAE accounted for higher extraction yield compared to other techniques, afforded higher TF, but not TP. Hence MAE under the optimised conditions is suitable for the targeted extraction of flavonoids. Conventional methods with lesser extractive value compared to MAE are appropriate for TP extraction, which are also recommended as safe, simple, cost effective techniques for large scale production.

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References

1. G. S. Kim, L. Zeng, F. Alali, L. R. Lingling, F. E. Wu, L. M. Jerry and S. Soelaksono, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1998, **61**, 432.
2. C. A. J. Misas, N. M. R. Hernandez and A. M. L. Abraham, *Rev. Cubana Med. Trop.*, 1979, **31**, 29.
3. N. Badrie and G. S. Alexander, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 1983, **7**, 1.
4. W. Y. Huang, Y. Z. Cai and Y. Zhang, *Nutrition and Cancer*, 2009, **62**, 1.
5. A. Kimbonguila, J. M. Nzikou, L. Matos, B. Loumouamou, C. B. Ndangui, N. P. G. Pambou-Tobi, A. A. Abena, T. Silou, J. Scher and S. Desobry, *Res. J. Environ. Earth Sci.*, 2010, **2**, 13.
6. R. M. Banik and D. K. Pandey, *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 2008, **27**, 241.
7. R. M. Smith, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2003, **1000**, 3.
8. V. Mandal, Y. Mohan and S. Hemalatha, *Pharmacogn. Rev.*, 2007, **1**, 7.
9. V. Mandal and C. Subhash, *Biochem. Eng. J.*, 2010, **50**, 63.
10. J. Hao, W. Han, S. Huang, B. Xue and X. Deng, *Separ. Purif. Tech.*, 2002, **28**, 191.
11. C. H. Chan, R. Yusoff, G. C. Ngoh and F. W. Kung, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2011, **1218**, 6213.
12. J. R. J. Pare, M. Sigomin and J. Lapointe, US patent 5002784, 1991.
13. R. K. Bhaskaracharya, S. Kentish and M. Ashokkumar, *Food Eng. Rev.*, 2009, **1**, 31.
14. A. Patist and D. Bates, *Innov. Food Sci. Emerg. Technol.*, 2008, **9**, 147.
15. X. Lu, J. Wang, M. A. Hamzah, F. R. Carolyn, J. R. Powers, J. Tang and B. A. Rasco, *Food Chem.*, 2011, **129**, 637.
16. M. Slavin, Z. Cheng, M. Luther, W. Kenworthy and L. Yu, *Food Chem.*, 2009, **114**, 20.
17. A. Q. Laghari, S. Memon, A. Nelofar and A. H. Laghari, *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 2013, **43**, 213.
18. H. Zhu, Y. Wang, Y. Liu, Y. Xia and T. Tang, *Food Anal. Methods*, 2010, **3**, 90.

